

MYXOPHYTES : NEUROTOXIC MANIFESTATIONS

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Blooms of blue-green algae are frequently associated with fatal episodes of aquatic fauna. Cyanobacteria produces two types of toxins : cytotoxins & biotoxins (neurotoxins and hepatotoxins).

Neurotoxicity are, by and large, secreted by certain species of *Anabaena*, *Aphanizomenon*, *Oscillatoria* and *Trichodesmium*. Of these neurotoxins, saxitoxin (STX) and neosaxitoxin, also termed as 'aphantoxins' are produced by *Aphanizomenon flos-aquae*. Anatoxin-a (ANTX-a) is an alkaloid neurotoxin produced by *Anabaena flos-aquae*, *A. spiroides* and *Oscillatoria*. The LD₅₀ in mice is about 200 µg/kg body weight as against 10 µg/kg dosages of aphantoxins. Mice injected intraperitoneally with lethal doses of ANTX-a die from respiratory arrest within some minutes showing symptoms like muscle fasciculation, heavy abdominal breath, cyanosis, convulsions and collapse.

Another neurotoxin - Anatoxin-a(s) {ANTX-a(s)} has similar characteristics to an organophosphate insecticide, being a potent inhibitor of cholinesterase. On treatment with 20 µg/kg bw of dosage (LD₅₀) animals show marked salivation, mucoid nasal emanation, ataxia, diarrhea, dyspnea and cyanosis. Anatoxin-b (ANTX-b), a neurotoxin with acetylcholinesterase activity; is more toxic than anatoxin-a and a(s). However, its exact nature and pharmacological action have yet to be worked out.

Key words : *Aphantoxins, Biotoxins, Cytotoxins, Hepatotoxins, Neurotoxins.*

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